

Studies in the Synthesis of α -Amino Nitriles

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Amino nitriles are the important intermediates in the synthesis of amino acids. These nitriles are found to undergo a variety of interesting reactions under the influence of various nucleophiles¹. Hence it was worthwhile to investigate a good synthetic route for the preparation of these important compounds. Plochel² describes the preparation of nitriles of type I through hydrocyanation of benzylidene aniline. We have further investigated this method and have given a modification to this procedure³. In continuation with our previous study, this communication describes the preparation of more new α -amino nitriles.

The nitriles described were prepared through the procedures A and B in good yield as reported earlier³.

In case of compounds No. 2, 4, and 9, the nitriles were obtained as thick oils which only solidify if kept at 0° for more than 48 hrs. In all the cases products were white crystalline solids. These are further purified by recrystallization from dilute alcohol, and their characteristics are recorded in Table I. The i.r. spectrum of these nitriles showed a weak absorption for $C \equiv N$ at 2255.60 cm^{-1} and $N-H$ at 3380 cm^{-1} . The weak absorption of $C \equiv N$ groups is due to the presence of adjacent hetero atom nitrogen⁴.

1. J. Yoshimura, G. Ohgo and T. J. Saito, *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **86**, 3858. and references cited therein.
2. J. Plochel, *Ber.*, 1880, **13**, 2118.
3. J. S. Sandhu, Suresh Mohan and P. S. Sethi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (In Press).
4. Suresh Mohan, Ph.D. Thesis, Punjabi University, Patiala, 1970.

TABLE I
α-aminonitriles

Sl. No.	X	Y	Nitrile Yield %		m.p.	Calculated	Analysis
			A	B		N%	Found N%
1.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	70	80	93	14.1	14.0
2.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	„	75	90	63	9.9	9.7
3.	„	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	70	85	97	14.8	14.7
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	70	80	90	11.1	11.0
5.	„	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	65	70	76 ₅	10.5	10.3
6.	„	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	75	95	86	11.9	11.6
7.	„	<i>p</i> -Cl	70	75	98	10.9	10.7
8.	„	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	75	80	95	11.0	10.9
9.	„	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	65	85	64	10.5	10.3

* Analysis was obtained through microanalytical service, C.S.I.O., Australia.

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